

1 Identification of glucocorticoid receptor (NR3C1) interacting proteins.

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7 The glucocorticoid receptor (GC) is a nuclear steroid receptor, like ESR1. It binds ligand in the cytosol and translocates to the nucleus where it interacts with factors that function in co-activation, transcription, and epigenetic modification.

8 Understanding how NR3C1 functions to exert the anti-inflammatory properties of glucocorticoids like dexamethasone is essential for control of glucocorticoid resistance.

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10 Optimal design of medical regimens can benefit from an enhanced understanding of the extent of
11 molecules NR3C1 interacts with. One such example is understanding from a translational standpoint how
12 glucocorticoids might interact with cancer therapies, like administration of glucocorticoids during
13 chemotherapy for TNBC.

14 A third reason that motivated identification of GC interacting proteins, and in learning more closely the
15 extent of shared interactions between ESR1 and GC was our finding that among the gene products whose
16 expression changed most significantly transcriptome wide both during resistance to endocrine therapy for
17 hormone receptor-positive (HR+) (luminal A and luminal B) and during resistance to glucocorticoid therapy
18 for inflammatory disease (asthma) was NCOA3. We recently defined NCOA3 as an ESR1 interacting
19 protein, demonstrating some level of shared nuclear co- activation between ESR1 and GC.

20 We found relatively high expression of the glucocorticoid receptor NR3C1 in androgen receptor positive
21 (AR+) TNBC, further illustrating importance of defining in detail the interaction partners and co-regulated
22 gene products for the steroid nuclear receptors NR3C1 (GC), ESR1, and AR.
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